

IMPROVEMENT OF FIBRE PLACEMENT ACCURACY IN CONTINUOUS TOW SHEARING PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

Automated Fibre Placement (AFP) is the state-of-the-art technology to produce complex composite aircraft parts. However, its main disadvantage is that it generally produces process-induced defects such as fibre buckling in steering process, which is required to lay up the tows following non-geodesic paths on a complex mould. Continuous Tow Shearing (CTS) was developed to eliminate the fibre buckling by using the in-plane shear deformation of the tow material. This mechanism can reduce the minimum steering radius by an order of magnitude compared to that of all existing AFP machines. When the steering radius is low, the layup accuracy is also superior to that of AFP.

Because of the active material feeding mechanism of the CTS, which is one of the major differences from AFP machines using passive feeding, accurate position and speed control of the head is crucial to improve the layup accuracy and quality. Although the developed CTS process could significantly improve the manufacturing quality of tow steered composite plates compared to conventional AFP processes, there is still some inaccuracy near the inflection point of the tow path during the steering process due to tow tensioning, which potentially causes tow pull-up in 3D application.

This research aims to improve the layup accuracy of the CTS by implementing a path and speed correction algorithm. The algorithm, which can calculate the head moving speed depending on the instant shear angle of each position during the layup, was developed. Different curvilinear tow paths were laid on a flat plate, and then the tow paths were scanned using high resolution image scanner. The algorithm was validated by comparing the reference tow paths with the actual tow boundaries obtained through image analysis.

Fig. 1. CTS prototype head steering a single 24K tow on a flat mould surface.